

Axis-Specific Haptic-Interaction Assistance Based on Concern For Others in Dyadic Collaborative Plate Control

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Abstract. Quantifying coordination in physical human–human interaction (pHHI) is difficult because classical mechanical metrics cannot separate individual operation skill from the coordination itself. We previously introduced Concern For Others (CFO), which isolates the operation change attributable to considering one’s partner, and showed through regression analysis that the pitch-axis summation component and roll-axis deviation component of Position CFO are the principal predictors of performance improvement in a dyadic plate control task. This work-in-progress paper proposes two CFO-based haptic assists, PSUM (augmenting pitch-axis summation) and RDEV (augmenting roll-axis deviation), and evaluates them together with their combination, a PD controller, and a no-assist baseline in a two-person Plate Control Task (eight participants, four dyads). RDEV alone significantly degraded velocity-tracking performance, likely through asymmetric force distribution between operators, whereas PSUM and PSUM+RDEV caused no significant degradation—suggesting that augmenting the summation component is safely applicable while amplifying the deviation component impairs velocity coordination in dyadic motor tasks.

Keywords: Physical Human–Human Interaction · Haptic Assistance · Concern For Others · Dyadic Collaboration · Plate Control Task.

1 Introduction

In human–human collaboration, individual characteristics strongly influence performance [1–4], motivating physical human–human interaction (pHHI) research to evaluate and improve it objectively [5, 6]. However, conventional mechanical metrics cannot separate individual operation skill from coordination itself [7–9]. We previously quantified the operation change induced by considering one’s partner as *Concern For Others* (CFO), and identified the pitch-axis summation and roll-axis deviation components of Position CFO as the principal predictors of performance improvement [10]. This work-in-progress paper designs two CFO-based haptic assists (PSUM, RDEV) and their combination, and evaluates them in a two-person Plate Control Task (PCT).

Fig. 1. (a) Overview of the CFO estimation procedure and (b) system diagram of the experimental setup.

2 Proposed Methods

2.1 Concern For Others (CFO)

CFO is defined as the deviation of each operator’s collaborative operation from the prediction of a per-operator solo model trained by a neural network on solo-task data [11] (Fig. 1(a)). Because the solo-model prediction already embeds that operator’s individual operation skill, subtracting it cancels the individual component and isolates the change attributable purely to coordination with the partner. We focus on the Position CFO (PCFO) computed in the angular dimension. Three group-level indices are derived from the per-operator CFOs: the *Total* (mean absolute), the *Summation* (mean absolute signed sum; cancellation among operators), and the *Deviation* (mean dispersion from the group mean; asymmetry). The proposed assistance uses the Summation and Deviation.

2.2 Proposed Assistance

Our prior regression analysis identified the pitch-axis Summation and roll-axis Deviation of PCFO as the principal predictors of performance improvement, while the Total–Deviation interaction was reported to induce strong nonlinear degradation [10]. Prior studies designed assistance exploiting partner role division (*specialization*) [1, 12, 13]; in contrast, our axis-specific design separates individual operation skill from CFO and augments different CFO components on each axis. We compared five conditions: **None** (baseline), **PD** (target-following), **PSUM** (additive gain on the pitch-axis Summation), **RDEV** (negative gain on the roll-axis Deviation), and **PSUM+RDEV** (both simultaneously); the assist gains were tuned experimentally.

3 Experiment

Four dyads (eight participants) tracked a rose-curve target by tilting a virtual plate through avatars (Fig. 1(b)) [11]; the study was approved by the Tokyo Denki University Research Ethics Committee (no. 08-032) with written informed consent. Each dyad performed the five conditions in a randomized within-subjects order. Each 80-s trial was recorded per condition; the first 20 s were discarded as familiarization and the remaining 60 s were averaged in 5-s windows. Conditions were compared using the Kruskal–Wallis test followed by Bonferroni-corrected Mann–Whitney U post-hoc tests ($\alpha = 0.005$). Performance was evaluated by the collective-benefit index [10, 14]: the difference between the dyadic tracking error and that of the best solo model, together with its velocity counterpart. Negative values indicate that the dyad outperforms the best solo model.

4 Results and Discussion

Fig. 2. Position and velocity performance for each assist condition.

As shown in Fig. 2, no significant difference was found in position performance ($H = 7.38$, $p = 0.117$), whereas velocity performance differed significantly across conditions ($H = 16.30$, $p = 0.003$). Post-hoc testing confirmed a significant difference between None (-3.05 mm/s) and RDEV ($+3.78$ mm/s) ($p = 0.002$). Because RDEV intentionally amplifies the roll-axis PCFO deviation, it induces an asymmetric force distribution between operators that likely impaired velocity coordination. In contrast, PSUM and PSUM+RDEV did not show significant degradation, suggesting that augmenting the summation component is applicable without compromising performance; the PD condition was comparable to None.

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Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange. Open questions from this four-dyad pilot include whether RDEV’s velocity loss is mechanical or cognitive, whether the axis-asymmetric Summation–Deviation structure generalizes beyond the rose-curve PCT, and how CFO-based torques should be rendered psychophysically. We invite collaboration across the EuroHaptics motor-learning, psychophysics, and haptic-device communities.

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